

Digital Medieval Graffiti

Using online-GIS to display and edit
non-geographical data

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Front cover image: A combination of a section of the wall as found in the system, and the normal map of that section (by A. Masinton). Image created by author.

Abstract

This dissertation describes the development of a system to view and edit a digital representation of the graffiti found on a wall in Durham Cathedral. The system can be accessed online and is built using only open source technologies. It is designed to be used by researchers to interpret the dataset and later by the general public to view the graffiti. Furthermore, the system is aimed to be an intuitive collaboration tool, with possibilities of further use with other datasets.

Samenvatting (Dutch abstract)

Deze scriptie beschrijft de ontwikkeling van een systeem dat het mogelijk maakt om een digitale representatie van de graffiti op een muur in de cathedraal van Durham te bekijken en wijzigen. Het systeem kan online gebruikt worden, en is ontworpen met enkel open source technologieën. Het is ontwikkeld om gebruikt te worden door onderzoekers om de dataset te interpreteren, en later gebruikt te worden door het publiek om de muur en de graffiti te bekijken. Het systeem is ontworpen als een intuïtief interpretatie platform, en heeft mogelijkheden tot gebruik met andere datasets.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

This dissertation describes the development of a system to view and edit a digital representation of the graffiti found on a wall in Durham Cathedral. This system will be used online by researchers to interpret the dataset, and later by the general public to view and explore the wall and the graffiti. The aim is to build a system as intuitive as possible, to allow anyone with a little computer experience to efficiently use the system. I will first provide some background information and the recording techniques, then discuss the aims and objectives and also give an overview of the theoretical framework. Chapter 2 describes the methods and how these have been implemented, while the last two chapters provide the results of this project, and a general conclusion. At this point, I would like to point out that Appendix F on page 54 contains all the information needed to access a live version of the developed system.

1.1 Background Information

In the summer of 2009, a team of researchers led by Anthony Masinton from the Department of Archaeology, University of York, carried out a survey of the graffiti

Figure 1.1: Photograph of the wall. Photograph by A. Masinton.

inscribed on the western end of the north wall of the Deanery of Durham Cathedral. In medieval times, the Deanery was used as the prior's lodgings. The area where the graffiti is located used to be the prior's private chapel (also see appendix 5 for a map of the cathedral). The graffiti is inscribed on a patch of wall of approximately 8 metres by 4 metres. The wall painting fragments visible in figure 1.1 date to circa 1450-1470, but were painted on top of an earlier painting, of which only the faintest stains remain. The graffiti is located between the two layers of paint: it is inscribed into the earlier painting, but covered by the later paint. The graffiti is very dense and depicts a range of subjects, from signatures to musical notation to rude drawings (A. Masinton pers. comm. 2010).

In general, graffiti is often covered with medieval paintings: whitewash and paint often obscures these inscriptions. The majority have probably not been visible for

several centuries, and are only now revealed due to flaking paint (Pritchard 1967). But the graffiti in Durham is located between two layers of paint, which means the graffiti can be dated precisely, which is relatively rare. Also, finding graffiti on wall paintings in itself is uncommon, as conservators tended to consider the graffiti as destructive and aggressive threats to the artwork, and were often seen as visual noise. As a result of conservation, graffiti is often destroyed. Furthermore, the graffiti that does survive on wall paintings are rarely recorded, if they are noticed at all (Plesch 2002).

Literature on graffiti is quite scarce as well. In some areas, such as the Mediterranean, graffiti has been studied to some extent, for example the graffiti in Pompei (e.g. Wallace 2005). In the United Kingdom, graffiti – especially medieval inscriptions – have never been given much attention. A study by Pritchard (1967) is perhaps the only comprehensive study done on the subject, but she also mentions: “The field of research is virtually unexplored in this country and its bearing on history and art has hitherto been neglected” (Pritchard 1967, p. xi). Although this statement was made several decades ago, it appears not much has changed over the years.

Graffiti can provide some very useful information. It informs us about attitudes and experiences mostly hidden from official histories. Graffiti provides valuable information about the life of people who normally do not get integrated into historical records. Especially an archaeological approach (in contrast with an art history point of view) has the potential to set the graffiti within a wider historical and social context, through the analysis of its character, content and location (Giles & Giles 2007). In this light, some research has been done on graffiti, for example by Giles & Giles (2007, 2010) and Turner (2006), but these studies mainly focus on periods after the middle ages. However, especially for the medieval period the historical record is biased towards the richer layer of society. Therefore, graffiti has even more value in

this period.

1.2 Recording Techniques

The main aims of the survey in Durham were to provide as comprehensive a record as possible of the surface of the wall and to create a metrically accurate drawing of the graffiti. This will allow the graffiti to be analysed and annotated by researchers of Durham University. Because this wall is in a section of the Cathedral that is closed to the public, this digital version of the wall will also make it possible to share this resource with the general public, and perhaps with visitors of the Cathedral (A. Masinton pers. comm. 2010).

In general, the standard recording procedure would be photograph wall panels and individual details in colour and black-and-white. Then, a series of acetate sheets would be affixed to the wall and the graffiti would be traced at a 1:1 scale (Giles & Giles 2007). Later, those sheets can be digitised into a vector drawing program, or CAD, where the complete survey can be interpreted and marked-up and where drawings can be prepared for publication. However, at the Deanery the majority of the graffiti are inscribed into a thin layer of plaster between the two layers of late medieval wall painting, as described in the previous section. The surface of the wall is too fragile to apply conventional recording techniques, which required the survey to be carried out without touching the wall surface (A. Masinton pers. comm. 2010).

Generally, when a touchless survey is required, a laser- or structured light scanning survey would be conducted. For this survey however, the equipment to perform such a survey was not available. Also, it is questionable as to how suitable such techniques would be in this particular case, as much of the graffiti are finely inscribed and lack almost any measurable surface depth. Another issue with such a scanning

survey is the cost of the equipment. This survey has been funded entirely by the surveyors themselves, with generous support of the Durham Dean & Chapter, who provided moveable scaffolding to allow the team to access the upper parts of the wall. This meant that the funding for this survey would be limited. For these reasons, an alternative survey technique was needed (A. Masinton pers. comm. 2010).

1.2.1 Photographical Survey

A new method of photographically-based survey was developed. The advantage of such a survey is that it can be performed with relatively inexpensive equipment and is relatively easy to carry out, solving the problems mentioned before. Two photographic surveys were conducted.

The first was a full photographic survey of the wall: a series of over 500 overlapping photographs of the wall. These were stitched together by computer to create a very high resolution image of the wall that is zoomable to a 1:1 scale. It in effect becomes a visual copy of the wall (A. Masinton pers. comm. 2010).

The second set of photography is the basis for the digitised measured drawing of the graffiti. The wall was photographed in a series of panels, each with a size of approximately 30 by 40 centimetres. The corners of each of these panels were measured using a theodolite, which provides the metric accuracy needed in this survey. Each panel was photographed nine times from the same location.

The first four photographs are taken with a laser dot from the theodolite in one of the corners of the panel. These four photographs are digitally composited to create a single image with four laser dots; an image containing the locations of four sets of coordinates as measured by the theodolite. The fifth photograph is taken without any laser dots and is the primary visual record (A. Masinton pers. comm. 2010).

The last four photographs are taken with four different directions of raking light.

The raking light makes it easier to see and define the graffiti, as it produces sharp shadows on the wall. These four images are digitally processed to produce a composite image that contains all of the raking light information for the panel in a false-colour image called a normal map (A. Masinton pers. comm. 2010).

1.2.2 Normal Maps and PTM's

Such an image can be seen as a map of the relief of the wall. The RGB values of each texel (or *texture pixel*) in the the normal map represents the x, y and z coordinates of a surface normal of an object at the point represented by the image. In other words, it is an aspect map showing which direction – north, south, east, west – each pixel is facing. (Kreuzer 2006). See figure 1.2 for an example of a normal map of a part of the wall. For an example of a normal map with a moveable light source, see <http://www.thomasav.com/normaltest.html>¹.

Figure 1.2: Example of a normal map of a part of the wall. Image by A. Masinton.

¹Unfortunately, this website is currently only viewable by Windows/Mac users

Normal maps are normally used by 3d games designers to produce the illusion of a geometrically rich surface without having to create the geometry itself, which saves CPU power when viewing these surfaces. When a normal map is applied to a surface and viewed under a moving virtual light source, the shadows that would be created by a light moving across a complex surface are simulated. This creates the illusion of surface complexity (A. Masinton pers. comm. 2010).

Some areas of the wall contain a lot of small detail. In these sections, polynomial texture mapping (PTM) was used by Sarah Duffy, a Ph.D. student at the Department of Archaeology, University of York. PTM is a similar method to normal mapping, but includes much more light data into the model, which increases the detail in the image. PTM's are similar to normal maps, in that they display light data in a composite image, using a series of differently lit photographs. However, PTM's also make it possible to display the image under different reflective conditions, which allows the user to virtually polish the surface. This creates dynamic shadows and highlights which enhances subtle differences in relief (A. Masinton pers. comm. 2010, Malzbender et al. 2001).

For this project, the normal- and polynomial texture maps allowed the surveyors to digitally trace the graffiti as they would using conventional techniques. Normally, a raking light is used during a survey to assist the surveyor in defining subtle graffiti, and allow him or her to correctly trace the graffiti. In this project, the normal maps and PTM's were used to create a virtual model of each panel, which allowed the surveyors to use a virtual raking light to assist them in digitally tracing the graffiti, effectively copying the methods used on-site to the virtual world. For this purpose specific software was developed by A. Masinton which utilises the capabilities of a 3d gaming engine to display normal maps and PTM's and manipulate the lighting. Using this software, it is possible to digitally trace the graffiti and export these drawings in a vector drawing format (A. Masinton pers. comm. 2010).

1.3 Aims and Objectives

The main aim of my dissertation project is to establish which methods are most suitable to display and edit spatial, non-geographical data online – in this case the gigapixel image of the wall and the digitised vector drawings of the graffiti – and subsequently implement these techniques. Of course, the results of this investigation will not automatically be applicable to every other situation where non-geographical data is to be used, as every project will have its own specific needs and problems. However, it can be used as a framework for similar surveys, and perhaps as an example of how methods which were not originally intended for this use can prove to be useful to display and manipulate archaeological data.

The main objectives of my project are as follows:

- Implement a method which allows non-geographical data to be displayed in an online system, overlaying the vector drawings of the graffiti over the photograph of the wall.
- Develop software which facilitates editing of the data in an intuitive interface. This will allow researchers in Durham to add their interpretations to the dataset.
- Create a public version of the system, which will allow the general public to view the graffiti, turn layers on and off and access more information by clicking on the graffiti.
- Perform user testing on the usability of both the editing and the public version.

I will describe how I have accomplished these objectives in chapter 2. But first, I will give an overview of the theoretical framework of my project and explore some broader issues in relationship to my work.

1.4 Theoretical Framework

Spatial information has been an important element of the archaeological record for a long time; maps and floor-plans have been used since the 18th century to record locations of finds and features. In general, much of the data recovered by archaeologists has an inherent spatial component. Everything we unearth and study has to be found *somewhere*, and will generally have one or more relationships with other objects (Wheatley & Gillings 2002). Some researchers (e.g. Clarke 1977) even claim that the information obtained from these relationships should be the main focus of archaeology.

Geographical Information Systems (GIS) are currently the main means to study spatial relationships and spatial data in general. But when looking at the definitions of a GIS as proposed by several authors, a confusion in terminology arises. Some authors (Burrough 1986, Star & Estes 1991) define a GIS as handling *spatial* data, while others (Wheatley & Gillings 2002) see GIS as a system handling *geographic space*. It seems that the terms ‘geographic’ and ‘spatial’ are being used interchangeably in the literature.

‘Geography’ can be defined as: “The scientific study of the earth’s surface and its various climates, countries, peoples, and natural resources” (American Heritage 2005). ‘Geographical’ can then be defined as occurring on the earth’s surface. GIS is mostly used for geographical objects and this geographical view is one which archaeologists are very familiar with.

The word ‘spatial’ on the other hand, can be defined as: “existing or occurring in space” (*Dictionary.com Unabridged* 2010), basically everything that has a location. The graffiti studied in this project can be seen as non-geographical spatial data, as it does not concern features on the surface of the earth visible from above, but it does have a spatial component.

1.4.1 Non-geographical Data & GIS

GIS were originally designed for geographical data, as the name Geographical Information Systems already suggests. However, GIS have been used to edit and display non-geographical, and even non-spatial data in several studies. Some examples of non-geographical uses include mapping the solar system (*3D Galaxy Map* n.d.) and genome mapping using GIS (Dolan et al. 2002, 2006). Examples of using GIS for non-spatial data include mapping the relationship between senses of words (Old 1999) and mapping citation information (Old 2000, 2002). OpenLayers, the technique used in this project (also see section 2.2.1), has also been used to map non-geographic data in some occasions. One of the examples is the Rosetta Project, which utilises OpenLayers to display the Rosetta Disk, a disc containing over 14.000 pages of text in over a thousand languages (The Long Now Foundation n.d.). OpenLayers allows the user to easily browse through this information, and give an idea of what the actual physical object looks like.

Although I will elaborate further on this in section 2.1.3, it is worth mentioning the study done by Ebdon (2007) here, as this project has a lot of similarities to my own. For his master's thesis at the University of York, Ebdon created an online application² showing an architectural drawing of a wall in Beverley Minster and vector drawings of the graffiti found on this wall. But although this application can be seen as a webGIS, it does not store any data beyond the drawings itself: it is not a spatial database.

None of the above projects describe the relationship between their work and the current debate on GIS. However, it seems that these kinds of novel uses of GIS can contribute a great deal to this debate.

²Which can be found at <http://braeside.org/beverley/index.html>

1.4.2 Place within current debate

It seems that in the last twenty years some of the main issues being discussed in archaeology are whether or not GIS and Virtual Reality (VR) are valid ways of representing the real world, if these technologies should be used and if so, how? Especially the subject of environmental determinism within GIS analysis has generated a large amount of literature. For example Gaffney (in Gaffney & van Leusen 1995) states that GIS is environmentally and functionally deterministic, and that this is caused by the restricted theoretical perspectives of archaeologists using GIS. Gaffney also suggests that these restrictions are caused by repeatedly using data types that already fit into the GIS data model, while whether these datatypes can allow valid descriptions of the past is rarely discussed.

However, Gaffney also mentions that when GIS is used to display where objects are and what the spatial relationships are between them, GIS can be helpful. In that manner, GIS is used to manage known resources, instead of trying to explain them (Gaffney & van Leusen 1995). In this light, this project escapes much of the common GIS criticism: it does not try to explain the graffiti, but is perhaps more of a recording than an analysis tool. On the other hand, the system can also be seen as somewhere in between recording and analysis, as it performs the former and makes the latter possible.

The debates see GIS as a mapping tool, and the analyses performed with it mainly try to explain the interaction between past societies and the landscape. Many authors forget that GIS can also be used for other purposes, and some conclude that “[GIS] offer an inadequate description of the archaeological record and a slavishly adaptive view of the world that is misleading” (Gaffney & van Leusen 1995, p. 378), discarding the validity of GIS altogether.

However, this project shows that GIS is not inherently inadequate and misleading. By using photographs, as well as vector drawings, objectivity is combined

with interpretation. This overcomes one of the other main criticisms of GIS: that it represents objects as a series of egalitarian symbols (Gillings & Goodrick 1996). Although this project does use egalitarian symbols (orange coloured polylines), the use of the photograph provides context and meaning to these symbols.

Chapter 2

Methods

In this chapter, I will compare a number of possible techniques, and describe how I used the most suitable methods to accomplish the objectives stated in the previous chapter. But first, I will give an overview of previous approaches used to display similar data online.

2.1 Previous Approaches

There have been some previous attempts at displaying graffiti online, from simple webpages to interactive Scalable Vector Graphics. I will discuss some examples here, to provide an impression of the context of my project.

2.1.1 Meashowe, Orkney

Meashowe, a neolithic cairn located on Orkney, contains a series of Viking graffiti inscribed into the walls of this monument. The Orkneyinga Saga describes how Maeshowe was looted by the famous Vikings Earl Harald Maddadarson and Ragnvald, Earl of Mre around the 12th century (Pálsson & Edwards 1981). These vikings left more than thirty runic inscriptions on the walls of the chamber, and

these represent the largest single collection of such carvings in the world.

It is prohibited to take photographs of these inscriptions as a visitor, but fortunately, these graffiti have been published online. On the website www.orkneyjar.com¹ it is possible to view some images of the runes and drawings and the website also provides translations of the runes and some background information (Towrie u.d.).

Although this website serves its purpose, it offers no interactivity and the images are more illustrative than a complete record of the graffiti. This is the most basic way of displaying graffiti online, and does not allow editing of the data.

2.1.2 St. Mary's Church, Ashwell

Another example is the medieval graffiti found in St. Mary's church in Ashwell, near Cambridge. In this church a number of walls and pillars are inscribed with graffiti, mainly consisting of Latin and Early English handwriting. On the website of the church² some of the graffiti can be viewed, and by moving the cursor over the images, the inscriptions are highlighted for better readability. Below the image you can view some information about the inscriptions, and a translation of the text above (Church website, Anon. u.d.).

This example uses HTML and JavaScript to display the images and animate the pop-up texts. Although this is a good way of displaying the graffiti and provides more interactive elements than the previous example, it does not offer the kind of interactivity my project would need. Just as the previous example, it seems this website does not function as a complete record and it also does not allow editing the data.

¹Full URL: <http://www.orkneyjar.com/history/maeshowe/maeshrunes.htm>

²Found at <http://www.stmarysashwell.org.uk/church/graffiti.htm>

2.1.3 Beverley Minster

The last example is a website developed for a master's dissertation a couple of years ago at the University of York by Dan Ebdon (as already briefly discussed in section 1.4). This project is an attempt to display an archaeological survey of the graffiti present at Beverley Minster. This survey recorded the graffiti and digitised it using conventional technologies and afterwards this data was published online³ (Ebdon 2007).

The method used to display the drawings is SVG, or Scalable Vector Graphics. This technique allows the user to view the graffiti and the surrounding architecture, and turn layers on and off. However, the SVG format is not natively supported by some browsers and provides no intuitive way of navigation. Also, in this particular project, there is no extra information accessible from the drawing itself, although some information on the graffiti is displayed elsewhere on the website. This website offers more interactivity than the previous examples and can be seen as a complete record of the graffiti, but it does not seem to allow editing of the data and is not very easy to use.

2.2 Choice of Methods

As shown in the previous section, none of the methods used in these examples are suitable for my objectives. None of them have an integrated editing functionality and it seems they do not allow interactivity beyond layer switching and pop-up graffiti.

For these reasons it was needed to develop my own system. From a large number of possible techniques, the following are the most likely candidates for this project: OpenLayers, Scalable Vector Graphics, HTML5 Canvas and Adobe Flash. To be

³This can be found at <http://braeside.org/beverley/>

able to select the technique most suited for my objectives, a list of requirements and preferable properties was formulated.

First of all, the software would need to be able to overlay vector layers on top of photographs, or the method would not function at all. In addition to this, the method would preferably have intuitive navigation, such as the navigation found in for example GoogleMapsTM, incorporating controls such as panning by dragging the map and zooming in and out using the scroll wheel.

The method would need to be supported by as many browsers and operating systems as possible, to make sure the information can be accessed by the majority of the potential users. Another issue is the size of the underlying photograph of the wall. As this photograph is a 1:1 representation of the wall, it in effect becomes a gigapixel image, with a size of around 600 MB. An image of this size would take up to 20 minutes to load on a moderate connection (500Kb/sec) and would also cost a lot of bandwidth on the server side. For these reasons some sort of loading time reduction is required.

The software would preferably be an open source system, to allow durability and flexibility and for general good practice. Also, the programming languages involved in adding the editing functionality were a factor: as I have some experience in JavaScript, PHP and SQL, those were preferable. The last requirement is support for an open standard vector drawing format, such as Geography Markup Language (GML) or Keyhole Markup Language (KML). These are different flavours of XML based file formats, which describe features using plain text. These formats ensure that the data will be accessible in the future, as they can be read by a simple text-parser and translated to a map. This is in contrast with proprietary formats such as AutoCAD's .DWG, which may become unreadable in the future if the company responsible for the format decides to stop support or if the company stops to exist entirely.

	OpenLayers	Flash	HTML5 Canvas	SVG
Vector overlay	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Intuitive navigation	Yes	Yes	Difficult	Difficult
Native browser support	Most	Most	Most, except IE	Most, except IE
Loading time reduction	Zoomify	Zoomify	None	None
Open source/standard	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Editing functionality	JS/PHP/SQL	Actionscript	JS/PHP/SQL	JS/PHP/SQL
Native support gml/kml	Yes	No	No	No

Table 2.1: Table comparing the properties of the software options. Positive properties are coloured green, negative ones red. (IE: Microsoft Internet Explorer, JS: JavaScript, PHP: Php Hypertext Preprocessor, SQL: Structured Query Language.)

In table 2.1, the four available techniques are compared based on these criteria. SVG and HTML5 Canvas are both open standards, but lack easy navigation, browser support and are unable to reduce loading time. Flash offers a lot of possibilities, but is a proprietary format and developing Flash requires software priced at around \$700. OpenLayers on the other hand is free to use and seems to have all the properties my project requires, as will be discussed below.

2.2.1 OpenLayers

OpenLayers is an open source online mapping tool implemented as a JavaScript Library. It is developed as a tool to display map data in web browsers, as a free open source alternative to GoogleMaps and similar web mapping solutions. The software allows overlaying GML or KML vector files on top of photographs and has similar controls as Googlemaps (OSGeo 2010b).

Also, It should be relatively straightforward to add editing functionality to OpenLayers, using some built-in variables, PHP and MySQL. Further information on the implementation of OpenLayers can be found in section 2.3.2.

Zoomify

OpenLayers can use Zoomify to reduce the loading time of the gigapixel image. Zoomify is a technique which converts an image into a number of tiles. These tiles are then processed to create different quality-levels for different zoom levels. When the whole image is viewed, all of the the low quality tiles are loaded and displayed. If the user zooms in on the image, only the visible tiles are loaded in a higher quality. This reduces the loading time, as only the relevant tiles are loaded, and not the entire 600 MB file (Zoomify Inc. 2010).

The Zoomify software that is used in this project is not open source. However, the output of this program is: it consists of a series of .jpg images and an XML file describing these images. If the proprietary version of Zoomify is no longer supported, an open source, cross platform version of the processing software is also available⁴ (Smith 2007). For the time being, the proprietary version is used, as the open source version is more difficult to use and install.

OpenLayers and browser compatibility

In general, OpenLayers is compatible with Firefox, Internet Explorer, Safari and Opera, apart from some minor known issues (OSGeo 2010a). However, because the system developed in this project uses OpenLayers in ways it was not designed for, the resulting code will only work on Firefox. For now, this is acceptable, but should be resolved in the future if the system is to be used on a larger scale.

2.2.2 Editing the Dataset

The editing functionality will allow the researchers in Durham to add their interpretations to the graffiti. Because this tool is to be used by researchers with limited computer experience, I will design an easy to use point and click interface. Clicking

⁴Which can be found at <http://sourceforge.net/projects/zoomifyimage/>

on a drawing will bring up a form in which data relating to that drawing can be entered. With a click on the submit button, the interpretation is sent to the server, where it will first be checked for integrity before being added to the dataset.

This interface will most likely need some sort of database back-end to store these interpretations. This database would need to hold information on the type of feature, the type of graffiti, the subtype of graffiti, a free text field and some sort of user tracking system. The database designing process is further described in section 2.3.3.

Another important function of the editing version is the ability to group features. Because a single drawing will generally be composed of multiple polylines, some sort of grouping mechanism would be needed. Ideally, it would be possible to simply select multiple features and click a button to group these features. Also, it should be possible to add or remove features from a group in an easy way.

2.2.3 Publishing the Dataset

The public version is primarily meant for the general public – people interested in medieval graffiti – but also for researchers from abroad. This version will use intuitive navigation, similar to the editing version. This will make sure the data is easily viewable by the majority of the public. Extra information on specific inscriptions can be viewed by simply clicking on a drawing, which will display information about the graffiti next to the map. It will also be possible to turn different layers on and off, based on the type of inscription, similar to the system on the website of Beverley Minster (Ebdon 2007).

Ideally, this dataset will be made publicly available on the website of Durham Cathedral, but this is not clear at the moment. To make sure the data will be publicly available, I will host the dataset on A. Masinton's public server⁵ for the

⁵<http://www.thomasav.com/durhamgraffiti>

moment. Also, I will deposit the drawings, the database and the created software at the Archaeology Data Service (ADS)⁶, to ensure durability into the foreseeable future.

2.3 Implementation of Methods

In this section I will describe how I implemented the methods as mentioned in the previous section.

2.3.1 Web Design

The web design for this project was but a minor issue. The website is intentionally simple in design, as it might be integrated with the Durham Cathedral website at some point. However, care was taken to ensure accessibility by most users, by using open standards and complying to the W3C XHTML and CSS standards.

The tabs at the right of the screen are used to display as much information as possible in a small portion of the screen. This is done so that the main focus of the website – the map – is as big as possible, allowing easy viewing, even at low resolutions. The styling of the page is mainly adapted to the standard style of OpenLayers, to give the page a sense of uniformity, but this can easily be adapted.

2.3.2 Data import

The first step in the data import process was to set up a platform to develop the software on. I decided to use LAMP (Linux, Apache, MySQL & PHP), an open source web platform, commonly used for all sorts of websites. To be able to easily develop and test the software, I decided to set up a ‘sandbox’ on my own laptop; a server for testing purposes that is not accessible to other users. I then uploaded the

⁶<http://www.ads.co.uk>

newest version every week to <http://www.thomasav.com>, A. Masinton's public web server. This allowed Anthony and the researchers in Durham to keep track of my progress and also served as a backup.

The next step was to install OpenLayers. This was done by simply copying `openlayers.js` (the JavaScript file) and some folders containing additional files to the web root. The first task with OpenLayers was to import the gigapixel image of the wall. This image was provided by A. Masinton as a series of Zoomify tiles. OpenLayers has native support for these tiles, which made it quite simple to import this data. An example from the OpenLayers website⁷ was modified to display the image of the wall (see fig. 2.1).

Figure 2.1: Impression of the gigapixel image of the wall as imported in OpenLayers.

Next, the vector data needed to be overlaid on top of the Zoomify tiles. As described in section 2.2, the preferable file types for the vector drawings were either GML or KML. Because it was easier to export to GML from the digitising software, this format was used here. In the initial stage of the research, no sample data was available and a dummy GML file was used to test the system. This dummy file consisted of a couple of polylines with no relation to the graffiti.

⁷Found at <http://www.openlayers.org/dev/examples/>

As soon as a sample set of the graffiti was available, it was attempted to load this into OpenLayers. In this stage, a number of issues were encountered. The first issue was that the GML exporter assigned feature ID's consisting of the letter 'F' and the feature number. This needed to be programmatically corrected so the file could be properly used in conjunction with the system, which assumes feature ID's to be numbers only. See figure 2.2 for an impression of the sample data in the system.

Figure 2.2: Impression of the sample data as imported and overlayed in OpenLayers. A painted braid is selected (in blue).

Another issue that was encountered during import was a slight shift in the drawings in relation to the zoomify tiles: the drawings are located about a centimetre to the left of the inscriptions as seen in the background image. This shift is most likely caused by the distortion of the background image, which is in turn caused by the stitching process. The vector data needs to be distorted to match the images, but that distortion is variable in a way that is difficult to correct for. Work is being undertaken to try and correct this shift, but it functions adequately as a proof of concept for the purpose of this dissertation (A. Masinton 2010, pers. comm.).

2.3.3 Adding editing functionality

In the previous section I described how all the primary data was imported into OpenLayers. The next step was to add editing functionality to the system.

Security

Before making the editing version functional, it was a prime concern to make the website secure, as these pages can be used to completely alter the database. To prevent unauthorised access, a login system was required. The first requirement was a basic users table in the database, which will be discussed further in the next section. This table stores (among others) the user ID, the username and a cryptographic hash of the password of the user. The password is hashed using MD5 (Message-Digest algorithm 5), this means that the password is converted to a 32 character string representing that password. This so called md5 string can not be translated back to the original password, but it is possible to check if the password entered by the user is the correct one, by comparing the md5 hash of this password with the hash stored in the database. This ensures that passwords are only known to the users, even if the database security is compromised.

Another safety precaution is the use of cookies. The login script will set a cookie on the users computer on successful login. This cookie contains the user's ID number from the database, and a random 32 character md5 hash. This hash is also stored in the users table and is replaced by a new random hash each time a user clicks a link. By comparing the hash in the cookie with the hash in the database, it is possible to check if the user is logged in. The user ID stored in the cookie will be useful later, when users can add data to the database (also see section 2.3.3 'AJAX & data entry').

The database

The database needed to perform a number of functions. First, it should hold user data needed for the login system, as described in the previous section. Second, it would need to keep track of edits: storing the changes made, the user and the time of editing. Third, it would need to store all information on the drawings. This function would need to store an auto-incremented group ID, the type of drawing (e.g. ‘graffiti’), the subtype (e.g. ‘signature’), the subsubtype (e.g. ‘Liber Vitae’), free text notes, the time of the last edit and the last editor. The last requirement is the ability to group features.

These functions can be performed by a relatively simple database, containing the tables `Users`, `Edits`, `Groups` and `Features`. The `Users` table is linked to both `Groups` and `Edits` using the `editor_id` field. `Groups` is linked to `Edits` and `Features` by the group ID. Also see figure 2.3 for the database design schema and appendix 5 for the data dictionary.

Figure 2.3: Database design schema.

Groups is the main table of the database. It holds all the latest information about the drawings on the wall and is the table that will be used in the public version to provide information to the user. The **Edits** table has the same structure as **Groups**, but holds every change made to the graffiti. This can be used to correct mistakes and even to return the **Groups** table to an earlier state. It effectively becomes a history of all the edits made to the dataset. **Features** facilitates the grouping of features, by holding a list of feature ID's and group ID's. The **Users** table is used for logging in purposes and user tracking.

The last three tables are lookup tables (at the bottom left in fig. 2.3). The contents of these tables are used to populate the dropdown boxes in the editing form. Putting these options in a table makes it very easy to add or delete options, in case any changes need to be made.

AJAX & data entry

The next phase was to make the editing process functional from a user point of view. To accomplish this, it was needed to make the drawings clickable, allow the web application to communicate with the database, and set up some sort of data input form.

Making the features clickable was easy to accomplish by adding a select-control to OpenLayers. However, tweaking the system so that the lines are easy to click on proved to be difficult. A couple of options were available: adjusting the line thickness, creating some sort of click buffer or using a hover function. Thicker lines would also cause the map to be obscured by the lines, making the total image less clear. A click buffer, where a feature is selected if a click occurs anywhere within a set number of pixels from that feature, would be a great way of solving this problem. However, the OpenLayers select function does not support this natively. In theory, it would be possible to create a script that would perform a similar calculation, but

buffering every line on the map (which could be thousands of line segments) is very intensive, and would require too much CPU power on the client side (Phil Scadden 2010, pers. comm.). The only solution remaining was to use a hover function, which highlights a feature when the cursor hovers above it. This, in combination with a slight increase in line width, gave satisfactory results. However, it was not possible to integrate the grouping information with the hover function. This means that only separate features, and not the whole group will be highlighted when the cursor hovers above it.

The next step was to design a basic input form, consisting of the fields type, subtype, subsubtype and notes, and making sure that this form could send data to a PHP script which can input or update information in the database using MySQL.

The third step was to get the feature id-number (FID) from the GML file when a feature is clicked and use this FID to build the form using a technique called Asynchronous JavaScript and XML (AJAX). AJAX allows web applications to asynchronously request and manipulate data from a server in the background without interfering with the display of the webpage, and then manipulate a portion of the HTML code of the currently viewed page (Moore et al. 2007).

In this case, the AJAX allows the system to (1) get the FID from the GML file using OpenLayers' `feature.fid` variable when a feature is clicked and (2) send the FID to a PHP script. This script then (3) retrieves the database record for the selected feature, (4) builds the form using the lookup tables, (5) selects the correct options in the dropdown boxes and fills the 'notes' field, and (6) sends the complete form back to the browser. Here, the JavaScript (7) receives this piece of HTML code and (8) displays it in the correct `<div>` element next to the OpenLayers map.

This form can then be filled out by the researcher. With a click on the submit button, the entered information is send to a PHP script together with the user's ID number from his or her cookie. The script then processes this information and

updates or creates a record in the **Groups** table using the entered information, the user ID and the current time stamp. This record is subsequently copied to the **Edits** table. When this is executed successfully, a message is displayed in the browser notifying the user that the data was successfully entered into the database, and the data entry cycle can be continued. See appendix 5 for a visual representation of this cycle.

Generating layers

One of the challenges that came up in the course of this project is that the layers are not rigid. The layers are based on the type of a group, and if a researcher changes the type of a group, the group also switches between layers. So because the layers are constantly changing, it was not preferable to save the different layers in separate GML files, as these would have to be rewritten every time a change is made.

Instead, the layers are created ‘on the fly’. This means that when the page is loaded, JavaScript takes care of putting all the features on the correct layers. This is achieved by:

1. Getting the group type and subtype information from the database and creating a layer for each of these.
2. Loading the GML file from the server, creating a **features** object.
3. Iterating through the features and for each feature check which type/subtype it belongs to.
4. Adding the feature to the correct layer.
5. Layers with no type information are added to the ‘Undefined Features’ layer.

Using the built-in OpenLayers feature ‘LayerSwitcher’, these layers can be accessed by clicking on a plus sign (+) on the right of the map. In this window, the

layers can be turned on and off. This is particularly useful for the researchers, as they can focus on specific layers, or show only those features still awaiting interpretation.

One of the problems encountered during implementation, is that the type ‘Graffiti’ has a number of subtypes, which should ideally be represented as sublayers. Unfortunately, OpenLayers has no native support for such a tree-like layer structure. Although there are some extensions to OpenLayers that could potentially generate a tree structure of the layers, it was decided that this feature was not important enough to implement at the moment. Instead, all types and subtypes are displayed in the LayerSwitcher in a simple list.

Feature grouping

Another unforeseen issue is that an individual feature such as a signature will almost always be made up of multiple polylines, while OpenLayers treats each polyline as a separate feature (as already briefly discussed in section 2.2.2). This discrepancy between ‘programming features’ and ‘real life features’ means that some sort of grouping of the features is required. Also, this grouping should be flexible: the researchers need to be able to add and remove polylines from drawings at any time during the interpretation.

This grouping can theoretically be accomplished in two main fashions: the grouping can be built into the GML file or the linking of features and groups can be done in the database. It seems the second option is preferable, as constantly reading and rewriting the GML file is more difficult than storing the grouping information in the database. Also, it is generally better to store attribute data separate from the spatial data, so both kinds of data can be handled by systems designed to do so. In this case, the GML file need not to be changed at all, and serves only as a set of drawings with feature ID’s (spatial data), while the database takes care of highly variable and constantly changing information *about* the features (i.e. the attribute

data).

In the database, the grouping is facilitated by a table (**Features**) that simply links features to groups. In the web application, it is possible to select a number of features and click on a button to group the selected features. JavaScript is used to send the FID's of the selection to a PHP script. This script then enters or changes the information in **Features**. See figure 2.4 for a diagram of this process.

Figure 2.4: The grouping workflow.

It is also possible to ungroup features. This is done in a similar fashion as grouping, but when the ungroup-button is clicked, the selected features are deleted from the **Features** table. There are some restrictions when grouping, for example, it is not possible to let a feature switch groups. The feature first needs to be ungrouped and then grouped with the correct group. It would have been possible to make this process easier and more intuitive if more time was available, but for now this workflow should suffice.

2.3.4 Publishing the dataset online

Making a public version of the web application was relatively straightforward. The editing version was adapted so that when a feature is clicked, a page with information is returned, instead of a form. Also, the grouping functionality was disabled and a layer relating to the grouping process was removed. Although the 'Grouping' tab was removed, the tabs at the right of the screen are still useful. In the public version one of the tabs is used as a user's manual and another for information display.

This application, together with the database back-end, is published on <http://www.thomasav.com/durhamgraffiti> for the foreseeable future. This will suffice for perhaps the next ten or twenty years, but as this is a personal server, it will go offline at some point. To ensure prolonged durability, some sort of archiving is required.

Future accessibility

To this end, all the developed software, the database structure, the database contents, the GML vector drawings and a set of metadata will be deposited at the ADS. This data will be supplied in open formats, to ensure future accessibility. The system will probably not be accessible in a working state, but rather as an archived version of the system. Instructions on how to set up the system on a live server will also be included. This will make it possible for interested parties to set up the system and adapt it if needed.

Another precaution taken is that at the back of this dissertation, two copies of the data and software are provided. This is done so that if one of the disks becomes unreadable or missing, the other serves as a backup. It is a certainty that eventually both of the disks will become unreadable, but that is why the data has been deposited at the ADS.

Chapter 3

Results

This project has resulted in a functional online-GIS capable of displaying and editing the graffiti. The developed software itself can be seen as the result of the research, and perhaps a reference to the CD-ROM¹ and the online system² should be seen as the main body of this chapter. A screenshot is provided here to give an impression of the system (fig. 3.1). Another issue that should be discussed here is usability testing, as how well the system works can also be seen as a result.

3.1 Usability Testing

Usability testing is an integral part of any design or developing project. Or, as Krug described: “If you want a great site, you’ve got to test” (Krug 2005, p. 141). After even a short period of time working on a project, the developer can not see the design freshly any more. The only way to find out if a website really works is to test it, as testing can remind the developer that not everyone thinks and knows the same. Usability testing has had a long history, and the basic principle behind it is relatively simple. To find out if a system is easy enough to use, watch some people

¹appendix E

²<http://www.thomasav.com/durhamgraffiti>

Figure 3.1: Screenshot of the system as loaded in Firefox from www.thomasav.com/durhamgraffiti. The orange lines represent the sample data, the blue lines are currently selected, and information about this group is displayed on the right.

trying to use it and note where they run into trouble. Then resolve the surfaced problems and test again.

Ideally, the editing and public version of the system would each be tested by their intended audiences: the researchers in Durham for the former, and a sample of the general public for the latter. Unfortunately, due to time limitations, it was not possible to test the system completely and satisfactory. The main user testing has been performed by A. Masinton, who raised most of the issues discussed in the next section. A number of archaeology students have also briefly tested the system. This testing has been done only on the editing version, mainly because time did not allow both the versions to be tested. All the features of the public version are also in use in the editing version, so if the editing version has been tested and adapted, the public version is not likely to bring forward any issues.

3.1.1 Feedback

A number of issues and problems were encountered during testing. The first problem was that the lines of the vector drawings were too difficult to select. This was mainly caused by the small line width, and was solved by increasing the width and adding a hover control, as described in section 2.3.3.

In grouping mode, the drawings would shift in relationship to the background image when the map is panned. This was caused by a bug in OpenLayers which was triggered when a layer was toggled on from a control in the browser. This issue could be resolved by slightly changing the grouping mechanism.

Another issue was that at one stage of development, groups would not automatically be toggled off on the selected-layer. This caused a number of bugs, from groups disappearing from the screen to errors in data entry. The error was caused by a piece of code which assumed the groups ID's to be an ascending array of numbers starting at 1. But when groups were created and deleted, gaps in the group numbers appeared, and broke the system. This was relatively easy to solve by slightly adapting the JavaScript.

Chapter 4

Discussion

In this chapter, I will conclude my research and discuss the issues brought forward by the development. I will also discuss some options for future research.

4.1 Technical Problems and Solutions

During the development of the system, a number of important issues were discovered that were impossible to foresee at the start of the project. For example the grouping of features, as already discussed in section 2.3.3. Problems such as these, and the solutions to these problems, are important issues which creating the application has identified. Although this can be seen as a purely technical matter, it is also an important matter for the project investigators to consider as well, as this involves a certain amount of interpretation. How this problem is solved also affects this interpretation, and the way the researchers look at, and deal with, the graffiti. In the current system, it is possible to group features, although the grouping mechanism may still need some optimisation.

Another problem that emerged during development is the fact that the vector layers containing the graffiti are highly variable, and will be changing constantly.

OpenLayers generally prefers to store separate layers in separate files, which greatly reduces the complexity of the JavaScript. In this instance however, it was needed to create the layers on the fly, by using information from the database. Luckily, it was possible to realise this feature within the constraints of this project.

One of the issues that could not be resolved completely satisfactory is the inherent tree structure of the layers. As the layers are build from types and subtypes of drawings, the layer switcher would preferably have some sort of tree structure to correctly represent this data schema. Unfortunately, OpenLayers does not support such a structure natively. Although there are some unsupported patches available that could potentially solve this problem, it was too difficult to implement these within the scope of this dissertation.

4.2 Enforcing Data Integrity

The system is very rigid: data needs to be entered in a specific way or errors will occur warning the user that the entered data is invalid. On the one hand, this perhaps discourages a free interpretation, but on the other hand also makes sure that the data that is entered is correct and uniform, making comparisons with other datasets possible.

It seems that interpretations of graffiti usually focus on the most interesting drawings, and the interpretations are often not consistent between studies. Often, not all the graffiti is even traced in the first place (Giles & Giles 2007). This system firstly forces all the graffiti to be recorded, and afterwards forces users to enter data correctly. It also provides a clear overview of which drawings have been interpreted and which have not, which will hopefully encourage researchers to interpret all the available drawings, instead of just the most prominent ones.

4.3 Use as collaborative tool

An unexpected use for the system that emerged during development and testing is as a collaborative tool. At the time of writing, the system is usable for this purpose. With some minor adjustments, the system can be even more useful as a platform for online, real-time discussion and co-operative interpretation. This would be beneficial for the current dataset, but perhaps even more so for more traditional archaeological drawings such as section- and floor plans. But more on this in section 4.4.3.

4.4 Future Research

In the current state of development, the editing system is functional, but not yet as refined and intuitive as needed. Ideally, the system needs to be optimised from a user point of view. Mainly the grouping mechanism and tree structure of the layers need to be further developed to make this system truly useful to users with little computer experience, although with a bit of reading in the user's manual anyone should be able to use it. Also, ideally the system would contain some sort of administration page that would allow system administrators to easily add and remove users and correct the database in case of mistakes.

4.4.1 Adding more base layers to OpenLayers

Another avenue of research that would be very interesting to pursue is combining the normal- and polynomial texture maps (as described in section 1.2) with the photograph and drawings within OpenLayers, and also add some sort of interactive re-lighting controls, such as those used in the Antikythera Mechanism Research

Project¹ (Malzbender u.d.). This would allow users to view all the scratches, bumps and flakes of paint not recorded in the vector drawings. This greatly enhances the usefulness of the system for other researchers, as this would enable them to take an extremely detailed look at the wall, perhaps even a better look than would be possible by actually looking at the wall itself. This would allow researchers to view the colours of wall painting, the drawings of the graffiti and the 3d reconstruction of the wall surface, all in one window, allowing greatly detailed interpretation and re-interpretation.

4.4.2 Augmented Reality

One perhaps more distant future development could be the use of Augmented Reality (AR) to view the wall itself and augment that image with the vector drawings of the graffiti and the information from the database. For outdoor AR, GPS is used in combination with solid state compasses and gyroscopes to determine the location and view angle of the viewing device, usually a smartphone of some sort. However, the accuracy of GPS greatly decreases when used indoors, and this has greatly hindered the development of indoor AR.

However, there are some technologies currently available that could provide a good accuracy indoors, such as Latitude, Longitude, Altitude (LLA) markers and image tracking. It seems that at the moment, junaio [sic] (metaio inc. 2010*a*) is the leading software in this area. Their smartphone application can use LLA markers to reposition itself without using GPS. Since the compass and gyroscope do work indoors, the phone can be pointed away from the LLA marker and still maintain a decent accuracy² (metaio inc. 2010*c*). It might be possible to supplement this with the image tracking capabilities of the application, which are able to recognise

¹See a working example of interactive relighting on http://www.hpl.hp.com/research/ptm/antikythera_mechanism/index.html

²<http://www.junaio.com/publisher/llamarker>

objects (or drawings) and ‘glue’ images or information onto the object in real-time³ (metaio inc. 2010b).

In theory, it should be possible to apply these techniques to the wall in Durham, and this would make viewing the wall and the graffiti a lot more informative and enjoyable as well. In practice however, as the wall lies in a section of the cathedral that is closed to the public, the application of AR in this particular instance has only limited applications. However, for similar projects in public spaces these kinds of technologies can really push information dissemination to the next level.

4.4.3 Using the system with other datasets

Although the system is specifically designed for the purpose of this project, the underlying principles are the same for any dataset. This means that the system can easily be adapted to display other types of data, such as floor-plans and sections.

Similar systems already exist, one of the most used online-GIS is the Integrated Archaeological Database system (IADB), originally developed in 1988 as an offline database system (Stead 1988). The IADB is a very extensive open source system, designed to manage data throughout archaeological excavations, from the initial recording, through analysis and eventual dissemination. It also incorporates a map element, in which features from the database can be plotted. The system can be seen as a virtual, online research environment. In essence, the IADB performs many of the functions also in use in my system. (Rains 2010).

However, because the IADB is so extensive, it is also more difficult to use than the system described in this dissertation. Although the developed system lacks a lot of the functions the IADB performs, in a situation where a simple, intuitive collaboration tool is needed, I think this system is preferable to the IADB.

³<http://www.junaio.com/publisher/junaio glue>

Chapter 5

Conclusion

One of the main aims of this dissertation was to establish which methods are most suitable to display and edit non-geographical spatial data online, in this case the image of the wall and the vector drawings of the graffiti. As described in section 2.2, the best set of methods consisted of OpenLayers for the mapping needs, PHP for the server side scripting, JavaScript for browser side scripting and XHTML and CSS for the website design.

The objectives of this project were to implement these methods and create an editing and a public version of the system, and subsequently perform usability testing. Except perhaps for the usability testing, the objectives were accomplished successfully, as described in section 2.3. The resulting system allows users to view the digital reconstruction of the wall in an intuitive and interactive manner, add interpretations to the drawings and group features. The end result is a bit ‘hacky’, but this was to be expected from the beginning. This is because the tools used in this project were not originally designed for this purpose, and so needed to be adjusted extensively.

Although some features could still benefit from further work, the current system is a useful tool and a proof of concept. It makes it possible to interpret the wall,

which would have been very difficult because of the fragility of the paintings. It also allows the general public to view this resource in an easy to use way. And last, it allows researchers from abroad to easily view and re-interpret the drawings and engage in discussion. In conclusion, the system will undoubtedly make interpreting and viewing the graffiti on this wall a lot easier.

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Appendices

Appendix A : Map of Durham Cathedral

Figure 1: Map of the Cathedral. The Deanery is marked red. ©The Chapter of Durham.

Appendix B : Data Dictionary

Table 1: Structure of table Groups

Field	Type	Null	Default	Links to	Comments
<i>gid</i>	int(10)	No			Group ID number
type	varchar(255)	No			Type of group
subtype	varchar(255)	Yes	NULL		Subtype of group
subsubtype	varchar(255)	Yes	NULL		Subsubtype of group
notes	varchar(1000)	Yes	NULL		Free text notes
last_edited	timestamp	No	TIMESTAMP		Timestamp last edited
editor_id	int(10)	No		Users (id)	Last editor

Table 2: Structure of table Edits

Field	Type	Null	Default	Links to	Comments
gid	int(10)	No		Groups (gid)	Group ID number
type	varchar(255)	No			Type of group
subtype	varchar(255)	Yes	NULL		Subtype of group
subsubtype	varchar(255)	Yes	NULL		Subsubtype of group
notes	varchar(1000)	Yes	NULL		Free text notes
<i>last_edited</i>	timestamp	No	TIMESTAMP		Timestamp last edited
<i>editor_id</i>	int(10)	No		Users (id)	Last editor

Table 3: Structure of table Features

Field	Type	Null	Default	Links to	Comments
gid	int(10)	No		Groups (gid)	Group ID number
fid	int(10)	No			Feature ID number (from GML file)

Table 4: Structure of table Users

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
<i>id</i>	int(10)	No		User ID
username	varchar(20)	Yes	NULL	Username
password	char(32)	Yes	NULL	md5 hash of password
logcode	varchar(32)	Yes	NULL	Random logcode, to validate cookies
full_name	varchar(50)	Yes	NULL	Full name of user
email	varchar(50)	Yes	NULL	Email address of user

Table 5: Structure of table Typelookup

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
<i>type</i>	varchar(255)	Yes		Valid types

Table 6: Structure of table Subtypelookup

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
<i>subtype</i>	varchar(255)	Yes		Valid subtypes

Table 7: Structure of table Subsubtypelookup

Field	Type	Null	Default	Comments
<i>subsubtype</i>	varchar(255)	Yes		Valid subsubtypes

Appendix C : Editing Cycle

Figure 2: The editing cycle.

Appendix E : Diary

Spring term

- Meeting with Anthony: discussed background information, technology and research questions.
- Meeting with Anthony and Julian: discussed research questions and requirements.
- Looked at some of the options: OpenLayers, Mapfish & HTML5 canvas.
- Wrote dissertation proposal.

Summer term

Week 17

Installed Kubuntu and set up a LAMP server on my laptop. This allows me to develop the software without having to connect to external servers, and solves the problem of renting server space. In a later stage it is probably still needed to move the software to a 'real' server, but for now this will work fine. Still working on how to access the server from other computers. Also set up OpenLayers to display a generic map, as I have no data to work with at the moment.

Worked on preparations for my assessed lecture, and dissertation workshop next week.

Week 18

Prepared and attended dissertation workshop. Positive feedback, but no suggestions or questions.

Looked at the different options in more detail, OpenLayers still seems to be the best choice. Also created a research schedule (see appendix 5) and started making a comparison table of the different options.

Week 19

Finished the comparison table. Unfortunately, while doing this my operating system crashed entirely, so I had to reinstall Kubuntu and set up my server again.

Prepared my assessed lecture and created a slideshow for the test run on Tuesday with some BioArch masters. Got some valuable feedback which I integrated into my lecture. Also found out I needed at least 5 more minutes, so I had to add some more slides.

Finished drafting my general introduction and started the 'recording techniques' subsection. I won't finish the whole introduction this week, as planned in the research schedule, because the lecture took up more of my time than anticipated. Will have to make up for this next week.

Week 20

Did my assessed lecture this week. Got some useful tips: the Archaeological Recording Kit and integrating the normal / polynomial texture maps into OpenLayers. I will look into these matters next week.

Finished the first chapter (introduction, recording techniques, aims and objectives) and did some work on my methods-chapter.

Week 21

Finished drafting the sections on previous research and my choice of methods. Anthony finished stitching the photograph together and gave me access to his server, which allowed me to download the Zoomify folders. After some modification, I was able to load the zoomify tiles into OpenLayers on my own server. Also uploaded the page to thomasav.com, which worked fine as well.

Designed the database, at the moment on the basis of info from Anthony, and made up some rows to test the 'users' table. See fig. 2.3 for the ER diagram. Also created a log in system for the website, using the 'users' table in the database and a cookie set at the users computer to easily identify the user later on.

Week 22

Worked on the login system: resolved some errors, added a salt to the password to increase security and put server-dependent variables (such as MySQL connection variables) in a separate file, which will ease moving the system to thomasav.com. Also copied the login system to Anthony's server, which after some tweaking worked perfectly. I also transferred the tables and their content to thomasav.com.

Wrote some subsections of the implementation section: some of the data import, security and the database. I also created a data dictionary for the database (appendix 5).

Had a meeting with Anthony on Tuesday: mainly talked about technical issues, but also about my introduction: I need to add a theoretical framework section.

Created a dummy GML file using QGIS and OGR converter, then loaded this file into OpenLayers. It seems to work well. I can now do some work on the editing functionality. I've been working on the data entry form next to the map. I created 3 data lookup tables to populate the type drop-down boxes. Also wrote the code that can check if the entered data is valid, and subsequently update the features table and copy the just created row to the edits table. I haven't transferred these new adjustments to thomasav.com yet, as they are still too buggy.

According to the schedule, I should have been working on importing a sample dataset, but because Anthony hasn't finished digitising the graffiti, I chose to create my own dummy data to work with.

Week 23

Wrote some paragraphs in section 1.4 (theoretical framework). Also did some more work on the editing functionality: last week the code could only update tables, I now added some if-statements to check if the feature already exists in the database, and if not: create a new entry.

Also started experimenting with some OpenLayers examples using JavaScript to display the feature number, which I will need to make the system work later on.

Week 24

I had to go back to the Netherlands this week, which meant I could not do as much work as I would have liked. I did however manage to use AJAX to get the feature number from the GML file when a feature is clicked, which is then posted to a PHP script which sends a form with the details of that feature back to the browser (also see section 2.3.3). It's still a bit buggy, but I'll debug it next week.

Week 25

Did some more work on debugging the system. Had some problems when I tried to move the system to thomasav.com, but managed to get it working there as well.

Also finished the AJAX for the public version: clicking on a feature now displays information on the feature next to the map.

Started work on trying to dynamically build layers in OL using information from the database. Wrote the PHP script that queries the database and returns a JSON string.

Week 26

Continued working on the dynamic layers. Mostly learned a lot about JavaScript this week, but I eventually managed to get the string passed to the browser by PHP into JavaScript, convert it to an object, and do stuff with it.

Also looked at creating a modified layerswitcher: because graffiti has subtypes, some sort of hierarchical tree structure is needed. Did find some mention of this in other projects, but need to look at this next week. First I need to get the dynamic layers working at all.

Week 27

Managed to get the layers to load dynamically, and put the features on the correct layer automatically using information from the database. This however created some problems with the 'SelectControls' which meant I had to rewrite some code.

Decided that for now, I will not pursue the tree-layerswitcher, I'll try to just put all type-layers on the top of the layer list, add a separator, and put all the subtype-layers at the bottom.

Also realised that a single drawing can consist of multiple features. This will not be easy to resolve, but I'll look into it next week, and discuss it with Anthony.

Week 28

Had a meeting with Anthony on Tuesday. Mainly addressed the issue of grouping the features somehow. Two main solutions seem applicable: grouping the features in the GML file, or grouping the features in the database. At the moment, grouping in the GML seems the most logical solution. Also talked about the future of the project after September.

Played around with a test GML file, trying to group multiple lines into single features. It seems that this should be possible, but now OpenLayers doesn't recognise the two lines as a single feature. I will probably need to hack OpenLayers itself to get this working.

Week 29

After a lot of experiments, it seems that trying to group the features in the GML itself will not be possible. Instead, I will try to group the features by adding an extra table to the database containing the relation between features and groups of features. This data can then be used to group features somehow.

Found out that there's an unsupported patch for OL that supports grouping of features. It adds an extra field to the features, and allows me to toggle groups. After much coding I managed to get OL to select the whole group instead of just one feature when a feature is clicked. I added another layer containing copies of the features and toggled all the groups off. When a feature is clicked, the appropriate group is toggled on, and displayed on top of the other drawings, which gives the impression of selecting a group.

Week 30

Mainly been working on how to create groups, add features and remove features from groups. This was quite challenging, and took up a lot of my time. For now it is only possible to create groups by clicking a number of features and pressing a 'group' button. Also corrected and wrote a lot of text, as the first draft should be handed in next week.

Week 31

Handed in my draft, got feedback from Anthony real quick. Corrected some issues, and also planned a meeting next week to discuss his comments.

Did more work on the grouping mechanism, mainly on checking to see if features should be added to a group, or that a new group should be created.

Week 32

Finished work on the grouping, also added a un-group function. Changed the layout of the page: added a nice divider, and tabs next to the map. Started writing everything up, as the deadline is in two weeks.

Week 33

Mainly been working on my text, but did some minor work on the system as well. Also created a manual for on the CD, on how to install the system on a new server.

Week 34

Finally received and imported some sample data from Anthony. After resolving some issues, got it to load satisfactory in OL. Anthony has also grouped and interpreted the sample dataset. This will provide a good working example as proof of concept.

Also exported the database into SQL queries and .csv files, to add to the CD. Finished writing the main text, started editing. Also performed some basic user testing, and resolved some of the surfaced issues. The grouping mechanism turned out to be buggy, and needed some rewriting. Also, the layerswitcher needed some adjustments to make it work fully.

Week 35

Finished editing my text, and burned the CD's.

Appendix F : Accessing the CD and server

CD

The CD's which can be found on the last page contain all the raw data, software and images used in this project, together with the developed code. Two CD's are provided, in the event that one of them become unreadable or if one of the CD's is missing, then the other CD serves as a backup.

Although the software does not run from a CD, it can be seen as an offline archive of the project. Instructions on how to get the system running on a server are also included on the CD's, if required. This dissertation is included as a PDF file, together with all the images in high resolution.

Online Version

The online version of the system can be found on:

<http://www.thomasav.com/durhamgraffiti>

Please note that at the time of writing, the system could only be used fully with Mozilla Firefox. The public section of the website is accessible to every visitor, but the editing section is protected with a username and password, to prevent any unauthorised altering of the data. To visit the editing section, please use username: 'reader' with password: 'graffiti'. If you encounter any problems with logging in, please contact me by email: alex.brandsen@gmail.com. Please note that although changes made to the dataset will not interfere with the research, any information entered into the system will be visible to other users.